

Original Article

Investigating the Impact of Consumption Values on Online Food Delivery App Usage: Evidence from Pakistan

Muhammad Abu Huraira¹, Syed Asad Hussain², Dr. Muhammad Waqas Rana^{3*} & Aliza Moiz⁴

¹ Senior Lecturer, Millennium Institute of Technology & Entrepreneurship, Pakistan

² Director Marketing & Planning, Millennium Institute of Technology & Entrepreneurship, Pakistan

³ Iqra University, Karachi, Pakistan

⁴ Head of Academics, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan

Abstract

One of the greatest inventions that the world has accomplished is the development of food delivery applications (FDAs) as it allows users to view a list of restaurants on the online platform, scroll through them, select the menu items, purchase, and get it delivered wherever they wish to receive. However, food delivery applications consist of various factors that determine its success. The following research paper aims to study the impact of consumption values on purchase intention in terms of food delivery applications. The three dimensions of consumption values chosen for the study are functional, social, and conditional values. A conceptual framework and underpinning theory are selected for the research paper. Smart-PLS software is used to analyze the data collected from the questionnaire of sample size of 115 respondents. The study gathered three hypothesizes from the literature review. The results concluded that all three independent variables; functional, social, and conditional values have a positive influence on purchase intention.

Keywords: Consumption Values, Purchase Intention, Functional Values, Social Values, Conditional Values

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INTRODUCTION

Online food delivery platforms often include a combination of food delivery applications and food-aggregator platforms that utilizes smartphone applications to select and order food from. These online food delivery platforms consist of platform that allows ordering food from them and restaurant-to-user deliveries (Wong, Chang, & Yeh, 2019). Typically, there is a notable change in consumers' lifestyles and preferences as the world experiences a constant growth in the online services, including the food delivery services through an online platform (Thome, Pinho, & Hoppe, 2019). Overall, with the increase the internet providers' growth and more usage of smartphones globally, typically in Pakistan, has enabled the increased utilization of food delivery apps, such as Food panda, Careem Now, etc. While online food delivery services can be done through an internet-based website, food delivery applications require a mobile application (Thome, Pinho, & Hoppe, 2019). In the following research paper, food delivery applications are considered to study the correlation between the variables.

Food delivery application (FDA) is a convenient courier service that utilizes technology to meet the end-user demands in reference to food delivery. Typically, a food delivery application consists of several different restaurants offering their menus to the food delivery application's users and providing their orders through the food-delivery company, where its rider will collect the order from the restaurant and dispatch it to the customer under a certain delivery period (Alalwan, 2020). In general, food delivery applications have long existed in the world since 1995, such as the World-Wide Waiter (waiter.com) as the first online services for food deliveries. On the other hand, Pakistan was introduced with the food delivery application concept in the year 2011 with Food panda. According to Statista (2022), Covid-19 had positively impacted the usage of food delivery applications as 71% respondents agreed that the pandemic had shifted their preference from dining-out to using food delivery applications to purchase from a restaurant (Statista, 2022). The shifting trends in the consumer preference for online food orders over traditional dine-ins have drastically increased due to

factors like Covid-19. According to Statista (2021), the expected growth of the users for the FDA segment accumulates to 2691.0 million by 2026 (Statista, 2021).

Additionally, the number of applications offering the services have also grown overtime in Pakistan, such as EatOye, Careem Now, Cheetay, etc. These platforms provide quality information to the users about a restaurant's offerings, pricing, and reviews, which enables customers to select a restaurant based on their preferences (Belanche, Flavian, & Perez-Rueda, 2020). Additionally, the FDA segment has increased drastically throughout the globe, which has made online food deliveries more common and are people are expected and recommended to use the platform (Statista, 2021). While there are many different factors that can impact the purchase intention of a consumer for online food delivery; however, this research paper will examine the correlation among consumer values and the purchase intention of food delivery applications (Kaur, Dhir, Talwar, & Ghuman, 2021).

Problem Statement

According to the literature that was used for the research, there were multiple research gaps that were identified, which revolved around the limitations of consumption values specific to Pakistan's food delivery segment and the in-depth understanding of the users' consumer behavior on the food delivery application (Kaur, Dhir, Talwar, & Ghuman, 2021). Specifically, the consumption values in terms of Pakistan's food delivery application sector is not researched upon extensively and requires study on it, particularly after the world was faced with Covid-19 (Ali & Khalid, 2020). To fill the gaps, the study aims to explore the consumption values specific to Pakistan's food delivery segment and also to understand the consumer values that impact the purchase intention. For the successful implementation of the research being conducted on the correlation between consumption values and purchase intention, the research involves four variables. The dependent variable is purchase intention, which is being studied through the independent variables, which are as followed: conditional values, social values, and functional values (Liu & Lee, 2018).

Research Objectives

The main aim of this research is to investigate the complex relationship between consumption values and buying intentions for the case of food delivery apps in Pakistan. In particular, it intends to identify how various facets of consumption values, i.e., functional, social, and conditional, impact customers' intentions to buy and utilize such apps. The study seeks to deliver an in-depth appraisal of consumers in Pakistan's perception of value in food delivery services regarding convenience, reliability, social influence, and situational influences that motivate purchases. Additionally, the study examines the relationship between functional values, including quality, price, and efficiency, and purchase intentions by consumers, ascertaining if functional benefits have an impact on user behavior. Equally, it investigates the interplay between social values like peer influence, social image, and cultural acceptance, and purchase intent to discern the social drivers for app use. Further, the research examines the effect of conditional values like promotional offers, discounts, and situational conditions on the intentions of customers to use food delivery apps. Through these interrelationships, the study hopes to provide useful insights into consumer behavior in Pakistan's fast-evolving online food ordering industry, finally informing business operations in creating strategies that increase user participation and satisfaction.

Research Questions

- What is the impact of preference values on purchase intention for food delivery applications?
- What is the impact of social influence on purchase intention for food delivery applications?
- What is the impact of information quality on purchase intention in reference to the food delivery applications?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Considering the nature of online application, i.e., to help consumers obtain a convenient way to shop whatever they wish to, in this context, the food delivery applications have revolutionized extensively to allow consumers have an optimized experience while ordering food (Hirschberg, Rajko, Schumacher, & Wrulich, 2009). While consumers gain convenience through food delivery applications, it is crucial to comprehend how consumers view these services and what impacts their purchase intention. The following chapter highlights each of the constructs that are used in the research paper, so the study's validity and legitimacy can be enhanced. Literature reviews of the previous studies that had similar constructs, nature, and correlation, i.e., a relationship between consumer values and purchase intention, will be studied and evaluated

comprehensively to strengthen the following research paper. Lastly, the previous literatures will be supported by the underpinning theory, i.e., theory of consumption values, and the framework utilized for this particular research paper.

Consumer Values

According to Kaur, Dhir, Talwar, & Ghuman (2021), consumer values are derived from distinctive ethnic and cultural backgrounds that results in different formation of manifestation, which is to be determined specific to their own contexts (Kaur, Dhir, Talwar, & Ghuman, 2021). After an in-depth research on multiple literature, there are three shortlisted categories of consumer values that this research paper will be examining. These categories of consumer values include functional, social, and conditional values (Kaur, Dhir, Talwar, & Ghuman, 2021). One of the utilitarian aspects that can explore a product or service includes functional values, which consists of quality information, price, reliability, etc. A qualitative analysis concludes that the functional values in reference to the food delivery applications obtains and revolves around the quality-of-benefits values (Gan & Wang, 2017). Another fundamental consumer value valid for this research paper is social values, which is typically associated with the correlation and relevance of food delivery applications in specific social groups. Hence, in accordance to the current study for this research paper, using food delivery applications enable consumers to gain social status in their social groups (Nair & Bhattacharyya, 2018). The third category selected in consumer values is conditional values, which refers to the temporally constrained advantages that food delivery applications may provide to the consumers under particular situations. In reference to this research paper, certain conditional values can also be seen as providing temporary functional advantages to the consumers when they are using the food delivery applications, such as timely deliveries, free deliveries, or lesser/no delivery fees (Talwar, Dhir, Singh, Virk, & Salo, 2020).

Conditional Values (preference values)

Consumers of the food delivery applications may draw perceived value from social or physical incidents—that is often referred in literature as, conditional factors linked with consumption (Ting & Ahn, 2022). By adopting specialized tools and techniques to boost their service visibility, firms may apply many conditional aspects to encourage customer purchases and build a desire for food delivery application consumption (Habib, Irfan, & Shahzad, 2022). For instance, such elements may refer to special pricing or promotional offers, decreased lead time for the product delivery, and discounts. According to Chandrasekhar, Gupta, & Nanda (2019), retailers often place an emphasis on advertising in order to make price-related conditional aspects more noticeable (e.g., discounted delivery in a specific region or for a specific period) (Chandrasekhar, Gupta, & Nanda, 2019). In addition, promotional offers and the exposure of product qualities like environmental friendliness may boost the perceived conditional value (Gan & Wang, 2017). As a result, we argue that making FDAs more visible may boost their perceived conditional value and preference among customers. Hence, we speculate that visibility and conditional value have a positive correlation that we'll refer to as "preferred value."

Social Values (social influence)

Consumption value theory also includes the concept of "social value," which refers to the perceived benefit that a person obtains from being part of a particular social group (Chakraborty, Kayal, Mehta, Nunkoo, & Rana, 2022). Customers' perceptions of social pressure play a significant role in determining whether or not they would use food delivery application, and subjective standards help explain this. Researchers discovered various aspects including social norms, social pressure, peer group impact and reference group opinion which may affect the decision-making process of the consumers. According to research, one's sense of social responsibility has an impact on environmental attitudes and sustainable consumption (Ahn & Kwon, 2021). Consumers interested with attaining social worth are motivated to acquire a trendy or certain social status by being part of the service consumption (Donsuchit & Nuangjamnong, 2022). Therefore, instead of a product's real functioning and performance, such consumers may pay more emphasis to features of the food delivery application that may boost their self-worth, symbolic value to others, and social approbation (Ahn & Kwon, 2021). Many researchers have addressed the relevance of experience purchases in getting social value, as they enable consumers to showcase themselves rather than the acquired commodity.

For example, there was observed a favourable link between social value and the usage of the food delivery applications (Donsuchit & Nuangjamnong, 2022). Upon subsequent analysis discovered status or social worth to influence purchase intention among consumers. Customers' self-perceptions and social standing were

elevated as a result of their stays in designer hotels, which in turn affected their future travel plans. Individuals' connections with others might also impact their choice to accept or reject an app (Ray, Dhir, Bala, & Kaur, 2019). The food delivery applications along with travel related application, for example, were shown to be favourably related with continued use of social value. More and more companies are emphasizing goods and user-generated content with an eye on social value, which has led to a shift in their marketing strategies. Conclusively, it can be stated that the social value or social status is positively connected with consumers' inclinations to acquire services via FDAs (Chakraborty, Kayal, Mehta, Nunkoo, & Rana, 2022).

Functional Values (information quality)

Information quality relates to the value, quality, validity, and usefulness of information that is the result of a set of information system (Pitchay, Ganesan, Zulkifli, & Khaliq, 2021). In addition, the speed and accuracy with which a system presents the user with relevant and usable information is a key component of information quality. Information quality is the fundamental predictor of a website's quality (Pitchay, Ganesan, Zulkifli, & Khaliq, 2021). Better information quality may inspire satisfaction and good behavioural intention. Consumers of the food delivery application create a good opinion of information quality when the information fits their expectations throughout the decision-making process and is presented in an acceptable way (Lee, Sung, & Jeon, 2019). Trust is built on the basis of information quality, which is the most fundamental means by which a consumer and seller may communicate with one another online. According to a study of the technology adoption literature, one of the most important predictors of future behaviour is confidence in the information provided. User choices made when utilizing systems is influenced by security and trust (Cha & Seo, 2020). Assessing the quality of information can be done in a variety of ways, depending on the target application and intended audience. It is claimed that relevance, timeliness, and accuracy as assessment items for information quality although few scholars stated that individualization, completeness, relevance, simplicity of understanding, and security affect success in e-commerce (Lee, Sung, & Jeon, 2019).

The sub-factors such as correctness, completeness, currency, and format are also included and analysed. Understandability, dependability, scope, and utility were the most important aspects of blog information quality. As is obvious from these researches, numerous categories of information quality have been offered but a consistent set of criteria has yet to be developed. These variables have also been used in a number of researches to perform single-dimension exams (Cha & Seo, 2020). A number of researches have shown a link between the perceived utility, perceived ease of use, and behavioral intent of information quality. Perceived utility was strongly influenced by the quality of the information. Perceived information quality in online buying had a favorable impact on perceived usability and convenience of use, according to the TAM model (Tanrikulu, 2021). The information quality has a major effect on the perceived utility and ease of use of services. In addition, the website quality had a greater impact on intention to use than performance expectations, effort expectations, social influence, and enabling factors. Consumers' confidence in online shopping was bolstered as a result of the high quality of the information they received (Bagot, Bagui, & De, 2022). When utilizing food delivery applications, the quality of information offered through the medium significantly affected perceived utility and simplicity of use. The information quality offered by social network-based communities had a major effect on the desire to engage in communities (Pitchay, Ganesan, Zulkifli, & Khaliq, 2021).

Consumer Values and Purchase Intention

It is empirically deduced that the customer values and consumers' attitude have substantial association with purchasing intention (Zvarikova, Gajanova, & Higgins, 2022). Social welfare value and environmental health value are key components of a good attitude toward social companies and have an influence on purchasing intention. Social business consumers feel happy because they can contribute to society via the purchase of social enterprise items and their consumption behaviour would be seen as ethical and moral (Gupta & Duggal, 2020). Consumers' affiliations with social businesses and their goods, as well as factual evidence, demonstrated the existence of two distinct groups: those who identify as consumers and those who do not. Factors of purchasing through food delivery applications were found based on the affiliations of social businesses and the qualities of social enterprise goods. Social business consumers place a high value on the features of goods including the pursuit of social value and symbolism, which were shown to operate as a factor of purchase (Gupta & Duggal, 2020). The pre-buy stage creates the perceived value of items and services, including the purchasing process, whereas the post-purchase stage relates to consumer satisfaction with the experience of utilizing products or services.

The previous component in satisfaction is one's sense of value, while the subsequent element is one's degree of contentment (Blazek, Michalikova, & Rydell, 2022). That is, perceived value is the component of satisfaction level. Some researchers have demonstrated that perceived value has a direct influence on consumer satisfaction. Numerous researches emphasized that perceived quality indirectly via perceived value or directly affect consumer happiness (Zvarikova, Gajanova, & Higgins, 2022). The service quality and value effect satisfaction not only indirectly via client satisfaction but directly associated too. The product quality has demonstrated to have an indirect impact on customer satisfaction through the concept of value. Perceived value, perceived quality, and consumer expectation are the main components of customer satisfaction (Bagot, Bagui, & De, 2022). The variables, an indication of the satisfaction level, were used to illustrate the direct influence of perceived quality on customer satisfaction and the indirect effect via perceived value. Perceived value has a beneficial impact on consumer happiness (Blazek, Michalikova, & Rydell, 2022).

Conditional Values and Purchase Intention

Prior research has revealed contradictory results while addressing the connection between the conditional values and purchase intention depending on particular circumstances or creating situational constraints (Toor, Husnain, & Hussain, 2017). Studies have demonstrated unfavorable connections between the behaviour of food delivery app consumers and conditional, such as while shifting to or introducing Islamic mobile banking, and the propensity to buy green items. Contrary to this, conditional value (such as subsidies and rebates) has a favorable impact on real estate purchasing intentions (Khan & Mohsin, 2017). The consumers' purchase of any food item through food delivery application, is typically in reaction to events that promote a desire for conditional (or preferable) value. Customers' desire to use online travel agents was recently linked to their preference value as a significant antecedent (OTAs). It was revealed that conditional value affordances had a considerable impact on Indian customers' propensity to acquire FDAs (Tandon, Kaur, Bhatt, Mantymaki, & Dhir, 2021). Conclusively, the conditional values also have immense influence on the individuals' choosing behaviour in the context of food delivery applications (Khan & Mohsin, 2017).

H₁: Conditional values have a significant impact on purchase intention.

Social Values and Purchase Intention

Song, Ruan, & Jeon, (2021) suggest that social values refer to influence of peers, family, friends, media, and society. The social value in various literature is described as how a consumer sees other people's opinions and their use. Therefore, involving how others' views might their purchase intention. Similarly, food delivery applications experience influence of social values greatly specially with the advent of food blogging and social media postings (Rusmevichientong, Ebrahim, Nila, Cheng, & Weiss, 2021). It was empirically deduced that peers or friends does affect one's FDA purchase intention greatly. Online comments or ratings might encourage users to adopt a technological system, like food delivery applications. People around may impact one's desire to purchase meals using online food ordering platforms, especially because utilizing the same technology gives them a sense of belonging to the same community or social group (Song, Ruan, & Jeon, 2021).

Social influence has informational and normative effects. The first effect occurs when information from others is taken as fact, like data from certain source is considered more credible due to his/ her previous record. Positive information impacts purchase intention positively (Amin & Tarun, 2021). Normative influence is conforming to others' expectations. As social influencer, some might emotionally engage to their favourite application of FDA. They may defend it on Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. This influences internet users' trust and opinion on certain application or brand (Rusmevichientong, Ebrahim, Nila, Cheng, & Weiss, 2021). This leads to multiple social influencers to be hired by FDAs to market their services. They utilize company-provided products to promote a product to their audience. Hence, social values promote peer purchase intention. Social impact is buyers' impression of referent group's online buying. Referent groups have comparable requirements and preferences (Amin & Tarun, 2021). Referent groups also impact purchase intention. Conclusively, customers' purchase intentions for meal delivery apps are influenced by social media, websites, or app reviews. Social value helps buyers commit and connect to a new development. Social values have great impact on online shoppers while utilizing food delivery applications (Ahn & Kwon, 2021).

H₂: Social values have a significant impact on purchase intention.

Functional Values and Purchase Intention

According to the literature definition of functional values, it is the perceived utility that is derived from a utilitarian, functional, or physical results. However, another definition relates functional values with the salient physical, utilitarian, or functional attributes (Zanetta, et al., 2021). Undeniably, functional messages have rapidly targeted customers, who are overexposed with them, which familiarizes many brands to functionality. Thus, it is less efficient to retain customer relationship from functional values as they have reduced in their durability (Zanetta, et al., 2021). In the context of food delivery applications, the functional values refer to components, such as durability, convenience, price, and reliability of the product. A product with an enhanced functional quality is when expected by customers, their perceived image of the product will enable them to have a higher brand satisfaction, commitment, need, and loyalty (Lee, Sung, & Jeon, 2019). According to (Yeo, Tan, Teo, & Tan, 2021), consumer choice and functional value have an impact on each other as one has a decisive influence on the other one. In many ways, it is also considered for functional value to be one of the fundamental drivers for consumer selection. In one of the researches being conducted on food delivery applications, it was observed that the information quality and purchase intention had a correlation as one had a significant impact on the other (Lee, Sung, & Jeon, 2019). Perceived information extensively impacts how customers decide for a particular product, so this impact is directly on their purchase intention in reference to usefulness and ease of use.

H₃: Functional values have a significant impact on purchase intention.

Food Delivery Applications

Food delivery applications or FDAs provide convenience to customers as it allows them to scroll through many food options presents on the application, search for the one they want, order the food from the application online, and eat it anywhere they like (Xiao & Dong, 2015). Typically, FDAs assist consumers in viewing the listed places they can order from, their menus and how much they are rated out of 5 for their food and services, options between cash on delivery and online payments, and availability of online tracking the orders placed (Dodds, Monroe, & Grewal, 1991). It is crucial to determine what drives consumers towards placing an order on food delivery applications, i.e., what is the purchase intention towards these platforms that users develop, which makes them purchase in the first place. While many factors impact the purchase intention of consumers in purchasing from food delivery applications, this paper focuses on the consumption values that have a prominent significance on the purchase intention (Gunden, Morosan, & DeFranco, 2020). Hence, opting for food delivery applications have a direct link with the information quality, social influence, and preference values of a user (Kaur, Dhir, Talwar, & Ghuman, 2021). In Pakistan, the leading food delivery application is Food panda, which the responses from the questionnaire for this research validates as more than 90% of the sample size responded to have been using Food panda as their preferred food delivery application.

Theory of Consumption Values

The theory of consumption values or TCV was primarily introduced in 1991 to understand the consumers' perspectives when it comes to their purchase intentions (Sheth, Newman, & Gross, 1991). This theory identifies and determines the reason behind what consumers choose to purchase and why they purchase a certain product. The TCV suggests that five dimensions of consumption values can impact a customer's choice behavior, including functional, conditional, social, emotional, and epistemic values (Tanrikulu, 2021). In recent studies, theory of consumption values was also implemented in the hospitality sector in reference to the online products and services, which could develop a successful correlation between consumption values and customer purchase intention (Kaur, Dhir, Talwar, & Ghuman, 2021). The following research topic is explored and researched upon on the basis of theory of consumption values. Among the five dimensions, this research paper emphasizes on three of the five dimensions; conditional, functional, and social values. Considering the main concept of the TCV, the three consumption values are tested upon to validate and correlate their impact on purchase intention in reference to the food delivery applications.

Conceptual Framework

Following the discussion in the above literature review, the variables highlighted and the existing correlation between the variables has assisted in the development of a conceptual framework for this research paper. The independent variables, as discussed above, are the consumption values, i.e., conditional values, social values, and functional values while the dependent variable is customers' purchase intention for food delivery applications.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypotheses

The above literature review has deduced the following hypothesizes for this researchpaper:

Conditional Values

H₀₁: Conditional values have no impact on purchase intention.

H_{1a}: Conditional values have a significant impact on purchase intention.

Social Values

H₀₂: Social values have no impact on purchase intention.

H_{2a}: Social values have a significant impact on purchase intention.

Functional Values

H₀₃: Functional values have no impact on purchase intention.

H_{3a}: Functional values have a significant impact on purchase intention.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The nature of the study conducted and the data collection process is quantitative, i.e., questionnaire was used to obtain numerical set of data for research analysis, so the correlation and influence of this study's variables can be concluded. Deductive reasoning was utilized to progress from exploring the underpinning theory for this paper to highlighting the hypothesizes. Thus, for the successful hypothesis development, the Theory of Consumption Values was utilized.

Target Population

For this research paper, the target population are all those individuals who have access to the internet, prefer food delivery applications to order their food, and live inPakistan. Additionally, the users know how to use smartphones effortlessly and have knowledge about the food delivery application services. The target population was approached personally and online. Individuals who were physically present on the premises were asked to fill out the questionnaire while many participants were approached through online mode, such as social media platforms, etc.

Sampling Method

As mentioned in the target population section above, the data is collected from participants who have access to the internet and are food delivery application users and reside in Pakistan, typically the metropolitan cities of the country, so the sample is drawn mainly from Karachi, Islamabad, and Lahore. Because the sample frame cannot be accessed; hence, non-probability sampling method was incorporated. Furthermore, convenience sampling, a type of non-probability sampling, was used to collect data from the questionnaire; hence, this is why three cities were targeted instead of targeting the entire country. This type of sampling is utilized solely for the convenient accessibility to the primary data and its proximity to the availability (Edgar & Manz, 2017).

Instrument Selection

The selected items for each independent and dependent variable revolved around a 5-point Likert scale. 1 represents 'Strongly disagree', 2 represents 'Disagree', 3 represents 'Neutral', 4 represents 'Agree', and 5 represents 'Strongly Agree' in the questionnaire. Under the consumption values, three items were utilized under each ofone: Preference values was adapted from (Tandon, Kaur, Bhatt, Mantymaki, & Dhir, 2021) and

it used a 5-item scale. Social influence also utilized a 5-item scale and was taken from (Yeo, Tan, Teo, & Tan, 2021). Lastly, the quality information consisted of 4 item scale and it was also adapted from (Yeo, Tan, Teo, & Tan, 2021). For the following research, all the scales were viewed and approved by the designated research supervisor. All the scales were present in the previous research papers that were revolved around similar domain, so the scale's credibility is well-established (Kaur, Dhir, Talwar, & Ghuman, 2021). However, the validity and reliability of the variables and their scales have been tested with constructive results displayed in chapter 4 of this paper.

Reliability and Validity Tests

In the SmartPLS software, to check the reliability of the variables, several Reliability tests were done. Primarily, Cronbach's alpha test is run on the data to measure the scale reliability, followed by RHO test and composite reliability test. For the Validity confirmation on the items, the Validity tests included Average Variance Extracted or Conversion Validity.

Selection of Data Analysis Tools and Techniques

Primarily, MS Excel was utilized to export the data collected from the questionnaire from Google Forms to an Excel sheet. Then, only the valid responses were selected, i.e., responses that were complete, did not miss any item, had accurate information, etc. SmartPLS software has been utilized to determine the Validity, Reliability, and Correlation between the dependent and independent variables. The data for this research was examined on the software to present the findings with the outcomes. To present consistency in the variables for this research and the scale items, Reliability test was run. On the other hand, since it is crucial that the research contains the correct scales for study and analysis, the Validity test ensures the correctness of it. Lastly, to conclude the relationship between dependent variable and independent variables, the Correlation test was run to deduce it.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The data collected from the questionnaire was tested through SmartPLS software, which uses the Partial Least Squares (PLS) path modeling method to determine the findings and analyze the data accordingly. The tests that were conducted on the software determined the reliability, validity, and correlation between the variables. Hypothesis testing was also done on the software. Additionally, this section also covers the demographic analysis consisting of the demographic variables used for the study. Lastly, all the findings and outcomes will be comprehensively discussed.

Demographic Analysis

An analysis was conducted on the demographic items on the questionnaire to determine the demographic results. The four demographic factors analyzed for the study are as followed: Age group, education level, gender, and preferred food delivery application used by the participant.

Figure 2: Age

The above figure highlights different age groups that the participants belonged to. There are four categories of age: below 18, 19-24, 25-30, and above 30. In the sample of 115 responses, 76.52% belonged to the 19-24 age group while 12.17% belonged to the 25-30 age group. The above 30 age group included 8.69% responses while below 18 had 2.61% responses.

Figure 3: Gender

The demographic analysis on gender signifies that out of the 115-sample collected, 47.82% responses were from male while 52.17% responses were gathered from female.

Figure 4: Education Level

From the following data collected in the figure attached above, the education level is analyzed to highlight the results. The responses collected indicate that 74.78% were either pursuing or had completed their bachelor’s degree while 13.91% were pursuing or had completed master’s degree. 6.08% participants were pursuing or had completed their higher secondary level whereas 4.34% were pursuing or had completed their PhD/equivalent and 0.86% responses belonged to below 10th graders.

Figure 5: Food Delivery Applications

The above figure indicates the preferred food delivery application that the participants from the sample use. The data analyzed shows that 95.65% of the responses preferred Food panda to order their food from while 3.47% chose Careem Now and 0.86% of the population preferred Cheetay. The analysis further indicated that no responses preferred Eat Mubarak and Eat Oye.

DATA ANALYSIS

Reliability

To determine the reliability of the scales of the dependent and independent variables, the test was run on SmartPLS. The tests included Cronbach's Alpha, RHO, and Composite Reliability. The results are as followed:

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha – Reliability

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Information Quality	0.822	4
Preference Values	0.831	5
Social Influence	0.775	5
Purchase Intention	0.894	5

Table 2: RHO – Reliability

Variables	RHO	Number of Items
Information Quality	0.846	4
Preference Values	0.846	5
Social Influence	0.782	5
Purchase Intention	0.900	5

Table 3: Composite Reliability – Reliability

Variables	Composite Reliability	Number of Items
Information Quality	0.881	4
Preference Values	0.879	5
Social Influence	0.922	5
Purchase Intention	0.838	5

Information Quality

From the above tests conducted on information quality to check the reliability of the construct, all three tests confirm reliability. Primarily, the Cronbach's Alpha value for information quality is 0.881, which is greater than the benchmark value of Cronbach's Alpha 0.7, so it indicates reliability. In the RHO test, the benchmark value is again 0.7 and the result shows a value of 0.881; hence, the construct is reliable. Lastly, the composite reliability indicates the reliability of the variables used in the study. The benchmark for composite reliability is 0.7, and the result shows 0.881 for information quality, which is greater than the benchmark and indicates reliability in the construct, its 4 dimensions, and the variable.

Preference Values

In terms of the preference values, the Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.831, which is more than the benchmark, 0.7. The RHO value was 0.846, which is higher than the benchmark of RHO. The composite reliability's result was 0.879, which is also higher than the benchmark set for composite reliability. The results indicate reliability in the construct, its 5 scale dimensions, and the variable itself.

Social Influence

The third variable was analyzed for reliability, which is social influence. The tests are as followed: the Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.775, which is greater than the benchmark 0.7. The RHO test showed that social influence had a value of 0.782, which is more than the 0.7 benchmark. Lastly, the composite reliability was 0.838, which again was higher than the benchmark; thus, concluding that the constructs, the 5 scale dimensions, and the variable was reliable.

Purchase Intention

The results indicated a highly reliable scale as the Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.894, the RHO value was 0.900, the composite reliability value was 0.922. Thus, it signifies that the 5 constructs are interconnected to each other and highly reliable for the research. Since the reliability was high, no scale items were discarded. The variable is reliable as well.

Validity

Table 4: Average Variance Extracted (AVE) – Validity

Variables	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Number of Items
Information Quality	0.651	4
Preference Values	0.593	5
Social Influence	0.513	5
Purchase Intention	0.704	5

Table 5: Discriminant Validity

Information Quality	0.807			
Preference Values	0.097	0.770		
Purchase Intention	0.502	0.430	0.839	
Social Influence	0.296	0.385	0.518	0.716

The above validity tests ran for each construct, items, and variable indicate that there is validity in each construct. Primarily, the construct information quality has an AVE value of 0.651, which is greater than the benchmark for AVE, i.e., 0.5; hence, it indicates that the construct and the dimensions used in it are valid for this research. Similarly, the remaining constructs are also valid. Preference values has an AVE value of 0.593 social influence has an AVE value of 0.513, and purchase intention has an AVE value of 0.704, which are greater than the AVE benchmark. Thus, the constructs are valid.

The second test conducted was the Discriminant Validity test, which is also known as the Fornell Lacker Criterion. It is the square root of AVE values and the benchmark suggests that each of the construct's square root value should be greater than other constructs' values. Hence, the results will indicate whether the constructs are unrelated, and according to the benchmark, they should be unrelated to each other for them to be valid constructs. The Discriminant Validity test results show that all 4 constructs are highly unrelated to each other as each of them has a higher value as compared to other constructs, and are unrelated.

Correlation - R Square

Figure 6: Structural Model

For the data analysis in this research, the researcher utilized structural equation modeling with the assistance of PLS-SEM 3. Presented figure 6 is the structural model which represents the relationship between the variables as deduced from the literature review and presented above in the research framework. The researcher conducted the bootstrapping procedure with the collected number of responses to authenticate the statistical importance of the variables and latent construct. To test the significance of the hypothesized relationship present in the structural model after checking the goodness of fit and measurement model, regression and multiple other tests were run on the data.

Table 6: R Square (Correlation)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Purchase Intention	0.467	0.450

From the above results, R square, in other words, the correlation tells the goodness of the data. The benchmark suggests that the result should be 0.67 or above to indicate that the variables are highly influencing each other. The benchmark also suggests that a value of 0.3 means that the influence of the variables on each other is low. The results of this study for R square shows a value of 0.467, which means that the variables (dependent and independent) are moderately influencing each other.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 7 - Path Coefficient - Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T stat	P Values
Information Quality -> Purchase Intention	0.387	0.375	0.078	4.990	0.000
Preference Value -> Purchase Intention	0.278	0.275	0.076	3.630	0.000
Social Influence -> Purchase Intention	0.297	0.311	0.078	3.808	0.000

From the above results shown in table 7, which is the path coefficient test to analyze the hypothesizes of this research paper, it can be deduced that all variables are highly significant. In terms of the p values, the benchmark is set as less than 0.05 to be considered as significant. Hence, from the literature review studied for this research paper in chapter 2 and deducing the hypothesizes from the literature review, the results indicate that the hypothesizes are complying with the previous literature. The p value for variable 1 is 0.000, which indicates that information quality is positively influencing purchase intention and is highly significant. The p value for variable 2 is also 0.000, which deduces that preference value is positively influencing purchase intention and is also highly significant. Lastly, the third independent variable's p value is also 0.000, which concludes that social influence is positively influencing purchase intention and is highly significant as well. All three-hypothesis deduced from the literature review are thus accepted. As per the previous study conducted by (Kaur, Dhir, Talwar, & Ghuman, 2021), (Yeo, Tan, Teo, & Tan, 2021), and (Zvarikova, Gajanova, & Higgins, 2022), the results in the studies accept the hypothesis; thus, they support the results in the current study.

CONCLUSION

The research paper was based on the study of the impacts of the consumption values on purchase intention in reference to the food delivery application sector. The study was conducted on Pakistan's FDA market and metropolitan areas of the country were targeted for data collection process. The consumption values that were strictly studied in this research paper were functional, conditional, and social values. According to the data collected and being analyzed, the variables had a significant impact/influence on the dependent variable, purchase intention. The results from this research paper assists in providing a meaningful feedback and insight to the food delivery application companies who wish to improve or enhance their services and offerings. In conclusion, it can be deduced that if food delivery applications work on the consumption values of users, they can positively influence their purchase intention and make them use and purchase from the food delivery applications.

Research Limitations

During the duration of the research and study being conducted, a few limitations were experienced and observed. Primarily, one of the biggest limitations of this research paper was its restriction towards only the Pakistan's food delivery applications to determine the correlation between consumption values and purchase intention. Since the responses depended extensively on online channels, such as social media and online messaging apps, many of the responses were considered invalid due to a lack of data or invalid/wrong input of information, which prolonged the data collection process. Furthermore, while the sample size of 384 (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970) was assigned to this research, it was a challenging task to gather all 384 responses on time; hence, time restraint was a crucial limitation for this research as only three months or so are assigned to complete the study and 115 responses were successfully collected. Additionally, the research was focused on three consumption values - functional, social, and conditional; however, other consumption values, such as epistemic and emotional values also impact the purchase intention. Convenience sampling

was used as a limitation due to the restriction on accessing the framework. Moreover, since the sample was mainly taken from metropolitan cities of Pakistan, it questions the biasness of the results and if they were generalized or not.

Recommendations

The study on the selected research topic was constructive at providing meaningful information about consumption values and purchase intention and their influence on each other in the context of food delivery applications. As the research concluded that functional, conditional, and social values have a positive influence on purchase intentions, it can greatly help the food delivery application companies in improving their services and offerings. Such companies can utilize this study at understanding users' consumption values and what makes them have a positive purchase intention. FDA based companies can refer to this research paper to examine the factors that have positive influence on purchase intention and adopt these factors accordingly. Additionally, the regulation authority should be established and functional in Pakistan, so the consumption values are strictly monitored and implemented by the food delivery application companies.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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